

Budapest University of Technology
and Economics (BME)

DEPARTMENT OF
POLYMER
ENGINEERING

PSEUDO-DUCTILITY IN LAYER-BY-LAYER HYBRID COMPOSITES THROUGH PRECISE CONTROL OF THE INTERLAYER THICKNESS

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Introduction

- Composites are stiff, strong and lightweight
- But their failure is usually catastrophic
- Ductility is needed for safety
 - High deformation at break
 - Detectable damage accumulation
 - Warning before failure
 - Residual strength after severe damage

State of the art

- **High performance composites: stiff and strong**, but **failure is sudden and brittle** with **little warning** and **poor residual strength**
- **Pseudo-ductility** with an **intrinsic safety margin** could **change design** approach and offer **major benefits**
- Excellent **pseudo-ductility demonstrated first with thin-ply UD carbon/glass interlayer hybrid laminates in tension**
 - Mechanisms: **fragmentation** and **stable delamination**

State of the art

- **High performance composites: stiff and strong, but failure is sudden and brittle with little warning and poor residual strength**
- **Pseudo-ductility** with an **intrinsic safety margin** could **change design** approach and offer **major benefits**
- Excellent **pseudo-ductility demonstrated first with UD glass/carbon interlayer hybrid laminates in tension**

- Mechanisms: **fragmentation** and **stable delamination**

The concept is then extended to:

- **UD IM/HM carbon hybrids**
- **QI IM/UHM carbon hybrids**
- **Visible damage:**
 - **Overload indicator**

(UK patent pending- no. **GB2544792B**)

Key challenges

- To develop pseudo-ductile hybrid composites based on standard thickness plies
- Reduce cost by using cheaper normal CF/EP plies instead of thin-ply prepregs
- Improve performance by increasing the CF/EP to GF/EP ratio in the hybrid laminates while preserving pseudo-ductility

Concept, design

- Pseudo-ductility was demonstrated with thin, high strain CF/EP plies or normal thickness low strength (high modulus) CF/EP plies
- Increase the mode II fracture toughness by interleaving nanofibrous layers and use normal thickness high strain CF/EP

Materials

Composite plies

Prepregs	Nominal fibre areal density [g/m ²]	Fibre volume fraction [-]	Cured ply thickness [μm]	Tensile strain to failure [%]	Tensile modulus [GPa]	Coefficient of thermal expansion [1/K]
AGY Y-110 S-2 glass/913 epoxy	190	0.49	153.8	3.7	45.6	3.20 · 10 ⁻⁶
Hexcel IM7 carbon/913 epoxy	100	0.58	95.8	1.6%	163.2	-0.103 · 10 ⁻⁶

Nanofibrous layers

Targeted areal weight [g/m ²]	<i>Electrospinning solution PA6 concentration: 8wt% (designation: 8PA6)</i>			<i>Electrospinning solution PA6 concentration: 15wt% (designation: 15PA6)</i>		
	Measured final areal weight [g/m ²]	Substrate speed [m/min]	Average fibre diameters [nm]	Measured final areal weight [g/m ²]	Substrate speed [m/min]	Average fibre diameters [nm]
2	2.3 (7.7)	0.20	108 (20.4)	2.44 (8.6)	0.80	267 (26.6)
5	5.26 (11.0)	0.12	103 (19.8)	5.68 (11.8)	0.36	243 (27.6)
10	10.92 (12.4)	0.05	121 (18.0)	10.66 (8.8)	0.22	280 (31.4)

Materials, manufacturing

UD glass/epoxy prepreg

- Manual lay-up of the composite prepreg plies
- Attaching dry nanofibrous layers to the prepregs
- Autoclave curing of the interleaved hybrid laminates at 125 °C and 7 bar

UD carbon/epoxy prepreg

Tested hybrid laminate configurations

Configurations Lay-up sequence: [G ₃ /NL/C/NL/G ₃] Key: 8 PA6-2: 2 g/m ² nanofibrous layer from a 8% PA6 solution	Fibre areal densities of the constituent plies	Measured thickness <i>h</i>
	[g/m ²]	[mm]
Baseline	[190 ₃ /0/100/0/190 ₃]	1.08 (1.9)
8PA6-2	[190 ₃ /2/100/2/190 ₃]	1.09 (2.1)
8PA6-2+RF	[190 ₃ /2+34/100/2+34/190 ₃]	1.14 (2.1)
8PA6-5	[190 ₃ /5/100/5/190 ₃]	1.11 (2.0)
8PA6-10	[190 ₃ /10/100/10/190 ₃]	1.11 (1.9)
8PA6-5+5	[190 ₃ /5+5/100/5+5/190 ₃]	1.07 (2.1)
8PA6-10+10	[190 ₃ /10+10/100/10+10/190 ₃]	1.10 (2.8)
15PA6-2	[190 ₃ /2/100/2/190 ₃]	1.09 (2.2)
15PA6-5	[190 ₃ /5/100/5/190 ₃]	1.10 (2.2)
15PA6-10	[190 ₃ /10/100/10/190 ₃]	1.10 (1.9)

NL- Nanofibrous layer
C- Carbon/epoxy
G- Glass/epoxy
RF- 34 g/m² epoxy film

Quasi-static uniaxial tensile test setup

Test results- Stress-strain response

- Pseudo ductility correlates with NL areal weight for the 8 PA6 series
- Different response for different NLs
- Probably due to different structure

Test results- Damage modes

- All series performed much better than baseline
- Mixed delamination and fragmentation for the non-pseudo-ductile series
- Close to borderline

Test results- Damage sequence

Delamination + fragmentation (8PA6-2)

1.92% strain (no damage)

1.93% strain

First Fracture of the CF/EP layer

Sudden spread of delamination

Fragmentation

2.8% strain

Damage saturation

Delamination around fragments

Fragmentation (8PA6-10)

1.97% strain

First fracture of the CF/EP layer

2.1% strain

Progression of fragmentation

2.8% strain

Saturation of fragmentation

Test results- NL structure

8PA6

15PA6

Nano webs

- Different diameters for different PA6 concentrations
- Nano webs for 15PA6
- Possibly different impregnation properties

Test results- Thickness of the interlayer

Test results- Thickness of the interlayer

Test results- Nanofibre volume fraction in the interlayer

Results- Cross section microscopy

- NLs are well infiltrated with epoxy and form interlayers between the composite layers
- Interlayer thickness is well controlled by the NL areal weight

Anticipated toughening mechanism

- Thick interlayer goes under proportionally lower shear strain
- Can accommodate higher displacements across the interface
- Can extend the damage process zone
- Expected to knock down singular shear stress at the delamination crack tip

Initiation of delamination in hybrid samples

a) Thin interlayer

b) Thick interlayer

Results- Longitudinal section microscopy

8PA6-2

8PA6-10

- Thin interlayer cannot suppress delamination completely
- Thick interlayer arrests delamination cracks

Test results- Effect of extra epoxy film

- Possible synergy between NL and epoxy film stabilising borderline response

Test results- Effect of stacking multiple NLs

- Stacked NLs with the same areal weight perform similarly
- Thicker NL stack improves pseudo-ductility and mode II fracture toughness

Test results- Mode II fracture toughness improvement

- Significant improvement of G_{IIC} from 1.8 kJ/m² (baseline) up to 4.7 kJ/m²
- Saturation is expected above 10+10 g/m² NL areal weight

Results summary- 8PA6 series

Configuration	Interleaved configurations [G ₃ /NL/C/NL/G ₃] (NL refers to the Nanofibrous Layer)						
	Baseline	8PA6-2	8PA6-2+RF	8PA6-5	8PA6-10	8PA6-5+5	8PA6-10+10
Measured thickness [mm]	1.08 (1.9)	1.09 (2.1)	1.14 (2.1)	1.11 (2.0)	1.11 (1.9)	1.07 (2.1)	1.10 (2.8)
Elastic modulus [GPa]	58.0 (2.7)	56.6 (2.6)	54.5 (2.0)	55.7 (3.8)	56.8 (1.5)	56.5 (4.1)	54.8 (4.2)
Knee-point stress [MPa]	1134 ^(a) (3.7)	1124 (3.0)	1070 (2.9)	1099 (3.9)	1096 (2.1)	1074 (3.9)	1014 (4.1)
Knee-point strain [%]	1.99 ^(a) (3.4)	2.02 (3.3)	2.02 (3.4)	2.02 (2.7)	1.97 (1.3)	1.93 (1.9)	1.87 (2.2)
Strain energy release rate @knee-point [kJ/m ²]	2.4 (9.3)	2.5 (8.3)	2.4 (6.9)	2.4 (10.2)	2.4 (6.4)	2.1 (11.1)	2.0 (11.9)
Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness ^(b) [kJ/m ²]	1.8 (7.4)	- -	- -	2.9 (8.1)	3.9 (6.6)	- -	4.7 (7.8)

(a) Evaluated from the load drop in the stress-strain curves of this configuration.

(b) Measured on [G₃/NL/C₂/NL/G₃] laminates with a cut in the middle of the CF/EP layer.

Results summary- 15PA6 series

Configuration	Interleaved configurations [G ₃ /NL/C/NL/G ₃] (NL refers to the Nanofibrous Layer)			
	Baseline	15PA6-2	15PA6-5	15PA6-10
Measured thickness [mm]	1.08 (1.9)	1.09 (2.2)	1.10 (2.2)	1.10 (1.9)
Elastic modulus [GPa]	58.0 (2.7)	56.8 (3.1)	57.0 (2.7)	57.3 (1.5)
Knee-point stress [MPa]	1134 (3.7)	1122 (2.8)	1113 (2.3)	1108 (2.2)
Knee-point strain [%]	1.99 ^(a) (3.4)	1.97 (4.0)	1.96 (2.2)	1.96 (1.6)
Strain energy release rate @knee-point [kJ/m ²]	2.4 (9.3)	2.4 (8.0)	2.4 (6.0)	2.4 (6.9)

^(a) Evaluated from the load drop in the stress-strain curves of this configuration.

Conclusions

- Pseudo-ductility was achieved in a range of interlayer hybrid configurations by inserting nanofibrous layers (NL) between the GF/EP and CF/EP composite layers.
- Nanofibres electrospun from 8% PA6 concentration solutions performed better than the 15% version.
- The thickness of the interlayers between the composite layers were precisely controlled by the areal weight of the NLs.
- Thick interlayers between the composite plies suppressed delamination because of lower shear strains experienced at given displacements across the interface. Interlaminar cracks were arrested in case of NLs with 5 g/m² areal weight and above. Saturation is expected at NL areal weights higher than 20 g/m².
- The G_{IIC} was significantly increasing with the areal density of the nanofibrous interleaves in the case of 8PA6 NLs, i.e. from 1.8 kJ/m² (baseline) up to 4.7 kJ/m² for the 8PA6-10+10 configuration containing NLs with a total areal density of 20 g/m².

Further details:

Marino S. G., Kuželová Košťáková E. , Czél G. : Development of pseudo-ductile interlayer hybrid composites of standard thickness plies by interleaving polyamide 6 nanofibrous layers. Composites Science and Technology, **234**, 109924/1-109924/14 (2023)

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Thank you for your attention!

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